

Composition as an Embodied Act: a Framework for the Gesture-based Creation of Augmented Reality Action Scores

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ABSTRACT

In a context where Augmented Reality (AR) is rapidly spreading out as one of the most promising technologies, there is a great potential for applications addressing musical practices. This paper presents the development of a framework for creating AR gesture-based scores in the context of experimental instrumental composition. The notation system is made possible by *GesturAR*, an Augmented Reality software developed by the author: it allows one to draw trajectories of gestures directly on the real vibrating body. Those trajectories are visualized as lines moving in real-time with a predetermined speed. The user can also create an AR score (a sequence of trajectories) by arranging miniaturized trajectories representations on a timeline. The timeline is then processed and a set of events is created. This application paves the way to a new kind of notation: embodied interactive notation, characterized by a mimetic 4D representation of gesture, where the act of notation (performed by the composer during the compositional process) corresponds to the notated act (i.e., the action the interpreter is meant to produce during the performance).

1. INTRODUCTION AND BACKGROUND

GesturAR is an application that allows to create, store, recall and organize trajectories in 4D (space and time) created from performance gestures detected through motion capture equipment. It has been developed for exploring of a new concept of musical notation: embodied interactive notation. In such form of notation, the act of notating (realized as a physical gesture in 3D space) corresponds to the notated act (the gesture that is meant to be performed). The transition from notation (realized by the composer) to the interpretation (realized by the performer) is mediated through an AR system (see section 3). This project relies on a background mainly including gesture-based notation, live notation and 3D/AR/VR forms of notation.

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1.1 Extended techniques and gesture-based notation

Both as a cause and a consequence of the increasing musical experimentation (especially from the 50s), the Common Music Notation¹ (CMN) has been pushed beyond the traditional forms of representation depending on different aesthetical purposes and composers. We can call graphic notation all those forms of notation that do not follow the traditional rhythm-pitch-loudness definition (as in CMN) and use graphic solutions not adopted in CMN. In particular, action scores [2] are scores where a prescriptive indication of the gesture to perform replaces the descriptive indication of the result to obtain. An example of action score can be found in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Lachenmann's *Gran Torso*, bars 95-97.

Gran Torso by Lachenmann (1971, Figure 1), presents graphic elements along with freely arranged derivations of CMN (Common Music Notation). In the example in Figure 1, it is possible to notice the use of the typical string clef: it represents the body of the string instruments; lines drawn inside the staff indicate the bow position. More importantly, in the first bar of Violin I appear two shapes with an arrowhead. They indicate form and direction of two different movements (to be performed together). In this score, as in numerous other that deal with some forms of gesture-based notation, the performative act that generates the sound is a compositional resource and part of the musical form. At the same time, the possibility to compose the gesture (alongside the sound) allows composers to create a brand-new set of timbral resources that were unthinkable

¹ "Common music notation (CMN) is the standard music notation system originating in Europe in the early seventeenth century." [1].

and unreachable inside the frame of traditional instrumental techniques.

1.2 Real-time scores

The increasing processing power of computing devices has enabled the possibility to include visual processing inside musical scores. Real-time scores (typically scores visualised on a screen) make use of some forms of animated notation. As they are essentially represented on screens, they can also be called *screen scores* and categorized as scrolling, permutative (elements of the score are moved, copied or cancelled in real-time), transformative (elements of the score are transformed in real-time) or generative scores (an algorithm generates in real-time the notation or parts of it) [3].

Such scores need specific pieces of software for being visualized. For example, the *Decibel Scoreplayer* is a tool developed specifically for real-time scores synchronized over a network [4] [5]). It can be used for scrolling scores, or for changing transparency of layers of superimposed static images. For example, in the composition *trash vortex* (2016) [6] by L. Vickery, different visual structures (used as musical notation) are revealed by such changes in transparency.

Advanced use of graphics and animations can be found in more recent scores, sometimes more focused on some idea of dramaturgy than on notation itself, projected towards film-making and gamification. *Genni* (2018) by P. Turowski is the staging of a story where the characters are geometric figures moving in a 3D environment. The score has to be interpreted by the performers as a form of graphic notation.

1.3 3D, VR and AR scores

Technical developments during the last decade allowed the utilization of the three spatial dimensions in real-time rendering, thus fostering the idea of 3D musical notation, as in [7]. In *64x4x4* by D. Kim-Boyle (Figure 2) for string quartet, for instance, the score is animated and nodes inside a 3D space are mapped to different pitches and playing techniques. For example, “colored nodes [...] represent various natural harmonics. The nodes are connected by a series of thin lines the color of which denote the strings on which the harmonics are to be performed” [8].

Figure 2. Kim-Boyle’s *64x4x4* string quartet.

More recently, VR and AR applications started being developed. The concept of *immersive score* is presented in [8]. The 3D score *5x3x3* (2016), for any three pitched instruments, is translated, in room-scale size, into an AR environment. The score becomes a virtual structure superimposed to the real world. It can be visualized by performers wearing HoloLens 1.

In *[P.O.V.]* (2017) by O. Escudero for saxophonist, VR glasses, electronics and projected video, the performer sees, in a VR environment, a 2D score and some short animations used as markers for some musical details, such as repetitions. Projections require lights to be turned off; the VR environment reproduces a score in the absence of physical light.

In *Hidden Motive* (2018) by A. Brandon, a graphic score is generated live by the composer and transmitted to a mobile device mounted on a VR/AR headset through wi-fi. The score is also mirrored to a projector.

LINEAR [9], in Figure 3, constitutes one of the first experiments making use of AR as a resource for live-generated notation and musical performance in the context of improvisation. The application allows one to draw perdurable gestures in the air. Those gestures, represented as virtual strokes formed by numerous virtual bodies, are linked to specific sounds. In order to produce some sound, the performer is required to draw and then interact with those virtual objects. Thus, virtual trajectories are both notation (as they indicate the gesture to perform) and control interface (as they can be used for producing sound).

Figure 3. Rehearsal using LINEAR.

Other forms of AR music notation have been experimented in the field of music education. Piano learning is by far the most explored topic, presenting already a high number of studies (e.g. [10–12]). Experimentations also exist for guitar (e.g. [13, 14]), violin or viola [15, 16] and non-western instruments (e.g. [17, 18]). In a good number of researches on AR-based music education it is possible to find:

- the use of some form of indication of position in 3D space (where to perform an action);
- the notation of event’s timing is not in space (e.g., on 2D paper or screen) but *over time* (i.e. events are notated when they are meant to happen and their duration is indicated through visual cues that last as long as the event they are referred to).

The piano roll (often used in AR piano education) is a good example: AR colored blocks come towards the per-

former in correspondence of specific piano keys (indication of position). As long as a block is “in contact” with the respective key, the player has to keep that key lowered (indication of time over time). Notwithstanding the interest of some solutions, notation in music education is usually adopted for teaching simple compositions selected from the traditional repertoire (compositions are notated in CMN in their original form) for beginners or amateurs. Evaluations in the studies show an increase in precision by using AR, a higher motivation and a lowered barrier of entry for beginners.

All the experiences above, from graphic scores to AR notation, extend resources and aims of the notation far beyond the CMN. It is possible to individuate a process towards the expansion of notation from the 2-dimensionality of paper towards the (interactive) space-time continuum. AR technology has the potential to further enhance these possibilities.

2. GESTURAR

GesturAR represents a first step towards the exploration of a new notational concept made possible by the recent developments of AR: the creation of 3D gesture-based action score (or interactive embodied notation, see section 3). The concept behind it is that, by notating quite exactly a movement in 4D space and time (as a trajectory), new aesthetic and experimental possibilities might arise. Current notational solutions for extended techniques are, in numerous cases, complete as they are: in fact, indeterminacy in the identification of the precise action to perform (almost intrinsic in prescriptive notation) leaves room for the interpreter to establish, within certain limits, an own relationship with the instrument and with the notation. However, the new and basically unexplored possibilities of AR for gesture-based notation present a promising perspective in which prescriptive notation reaches a high degree of predictability in terms of gesture and sound result, especially where complex actions, difficult to notate on paper, come into play.

GesturAR allows one to draw, store and play back trajectories of gestures (with the sound they produce) performed on any acoustic instrument having a vibrating surface. For example, metal sheets, gongs, toms, bass drums, piano strings, strings or harp could be suitable instruments. In fact, the sound of all of the mentioned instruments is modified by trajectories performed on their surfaces (or along and across the strings). On the contrary, woodwinds or brass instruments players could hardly make any use of GesturAR, as the sound is almost exclusively controlled through lips position, blow emission and fingerings. The application has been developed thinking about musical performance on acoustic instruments. In GesturAR, trajectories are recorded with the original speed and internal articulation of the gesture and will maintain the exact temporal proportions when played back.

For example, let’s consider a setup formed by a tam-tam and two spherical magnets (one per side of the tam-tam, held together across the instrument’s body by the magnetic force, Figure 4). By moving the magnets on the surface,

the timbre of the instrument is changed according to the position of the magnet and the perceived pitch(es) (if any) will be shifted downwards or upwards. The system provides indication about the position of those magnets in time (therefore about the result, which is unique given a specific instrument and a specific position) directly on the instrument itself.

Figure 4. A magnet moved on a tam-tam. The second magnet is in the back of the instrument.

Another example (Figure 5) can be seen on the piano played with a rattle-singing magnet (similar effects can be achieved, in general, with metal objects). In that case, the position of the magnet determines the production of two pitches at any given time: the metal object divides the string in two distinct vibrating parts, each of them producing a different pitch. In normal notation, the indication of the precise gesture related to a precise pitch result would present several issues. In GesturAR, the trajectory and the position of the magnet at any given time can be delivered in real-time and in space.

Figure 5. The use of a rattle-singing magnet on piano strings.

The visual representation of gesture shown directly on the vibrating body (such as strings or metal plates) could provide a new, intuitive framework for writing, rehearsing and performing some specific sets of extended techniques. From the performer’s point of view, it is possible to follow the trajectories in real-time on the instrument instead of learning, from a paper score, the precise gesture, its timing and its approximate timbral result. From the composer’s

point of view, the notational process allows a direct and intuitive way of storing and retrieving information about the wanted gesture and, at the same time, the intended sound result.

2.1 Technical framework

The framework is composed of:

- software developed in Unity3D/C#, used for motion capture, data processing (headset and trackers position and orientation) and graphics rendering; connected through OSC protocol to:
- Max/MSP patch handling audio processing and playing sound files;
- 1 HTC Vive Pro headset;
- 1 HTC Vive Tracker;
- 1 LeapMotion²;
- 1 contact microphone.

2.2 Functions

2.2.1 Recording trajectories

The system makes use of LeapMotion for detecting the fingers' position at each video frame. The detection is performed using the LeapMotion plugin for Unity. There is also a sound processing unit (in Max/MSP) used for detecting when the instrument is played (details explained in 2.2.4). The position of the instrument (tam-tam, in this case) in space is detected by using a Vive Tracker. This way, the user does not need to manually set the position of the instrument after every reboot of the software.

In GesturAR, a User Interface (UI) is created around the instrument. It can be used for triggering different functions: *Start Recording*, *Stop Recording*, *Cancel*, *Save*, *Load*, *Write Score*, *Process Score*. The interaction with virtual buttons is enabled by the hands' position detection provided by the LeapMotion. The hands have virtual colliders attached to them, used for detecting collisions with virtual objects.

When the user's hand collides with the *Start Recording* button, the system waits for the user to start playing (by using an envelope follower implemented in Max/MSP, see 2.2.4) Then it starts recording the position of the left index finger-tip at each frame (Figure 6) and creates a trajectory out of it. When the user stops playing (according to the envelope follower), the system stops recording the position.

² Device for skeletal hand-tracking, providing position and orientation for each knuckle, the palm and the wrist.

Figure 6. When the recording is activated and the instrument is played, the software starts recording the position of the fingertip frame by frame.

If the user hits *Save*, the system stores the trajectory as a *.json* file and saves it for later use. The trajectory can be played back by reading consequent positional data in the *.json* file in consequent video frames. By interacting with the *Cancel* button, the user can erase the last recorded trajectory.

2.2.2 Loading trajectories

Figure 7. The user can select different pre-stored trajectories by “pressing” with the hand the red square containing its miniaturized shape.

After the user presses the *Load* button, an additional part of the UI is rendered near to the instrument, presenting all the trajectories already stored in the system. Each of them is represented as a miniaturised collection of spheres (one per sampling point) inscribed inside a red blocks. The user can select one trajectory by interacting with the relative blocks (Figure 7). The selected trajectory is then rendered on the instrument, in full scale (Figure 8). The original gesture can be played back as a line that moves from one sampling point to the next, preserving the original speed of the gesture (Figure 9).

Figure 8. The selected trajectory is rendered over the real instrument as a collection of spheres, indicating the sampling points in space.

Figure 9. Trajectory playback.

2.2.3 Creating the score

By selecting *Write Score*, a timeline (a transparent white rectangle) is activated (Figure 10). The user will have the possibility to select trajectories from a menu (still in miniaturized form inside red blocks). When a trajectory is selected, a copy of it is created inside the timeline. By using a *grab gesture*³, the user can move trajectories inside the timeline. At the current stage of development, only one trajectory at a time is possible. Inside the timeline, durations are proportionally represented. The length of blocks is proportional to the duration of each gesture and the space between different gestures is proportional to the duration of the silence (i.e., no gesture rendered on the instrument) between consecutive gestures. Once the timeline has been arranged, the user can press the *Process* button and the AR action score will be created and played back.

³ An interaction gesture consisting in closing the fist and moving it. This gesture is typically used in AR/VR for moving virtual objects.

Figure 10. The user positioning trajectories on the timeline.

The score consists of a series of lines drawn on the instrument, representing the gestures in the given order on the timeline, with their original speed and with rests between gestures having a duration proportional to the space between consecutive red blocks.

2.2.4 Max/MSP

The Max/MSP patch has two functionalities:

- understanding when the instrument is played for triggering the recording inside the AR software;
- storing and recalling the recorded sound linked to each trajectory.

The first function is accomplished by using an envelope following algorithm based on spectral magnitude values, averaged over 10 consecutive audio frames. When the values pass the minimal threshold, a *start* message is sent through OSC (Open Sound Control) to the AR software, that starts recording the trajectory. When the values fall back under the threshold, a *stop* message is sent to the AR software. The second function is accomplished by storing the sound produced by each trajectory inside a buffer. If the user decides to save the trajectory (inside the AR software) a *save* message is sent through OSC from the AR software to Max/MSP and the content of the buffer is saved to a sound file. When a trajectory in the AR software is selected and played back, a *play* message is sent from the AR software to Max/MSP and the file associated to the trajectory is played back.

3. EMBODIED INTERACTIVE NOTATION

GesturAR represents the first exploration into a new type of notation that could be called *embodied interactive notation*: the notation is created as a direct consequence of an embodied act (detected through sensors) and is a 4D representation in space and time of the original gesture, in the form of a trajectory or some other kind of spatial marking. The gesture that creates the notation and the notated act coincide, as the notational moment is also a performative one (the notation is generated as a consequence of a gesture that produces sound). Following from this description, an AR representation of gesture in space has a two-fold interpretation: from one point of view, it is, as said, a new type

of musical notation, with specific possibilities and affordances, still largely unexplored. On the other side, it has a very specific technical profile, as it allows a precise representation of trajectory and timing of complex gestures, in a way that is precluded to notation on paper.

This particular form of notation implies a peculiar relationship between composer and interpreter: the notation keeps trace of the performative moment from which it was generated. For notating, the composer has to be a performer. For interpreting, the performer has to redo what the composer did in the moment of creation.

Embodied interactive notation, as realised in GesturAR, also implies a peculiar approach to rhythm. Musical time is not notated in a proportional or symbolic way. The system is not meant to represent a precise rhythm subdivided in discrete values of duration (as it happens, for example, with quavers and semiquavers in CMN). In fact, while in the usual practice rhythm is notated in space (e.g., on paper or on a screen), GesturAR notates time *over time*: information about starting moment and duration of events is provided in the moment in which the event is meant to happen and as long as the event is meant to last. Such a relationship with time is quite intrinsic in AR forms of notation, as shown in numerous research papers on music education that make use of some real-time positional indication (e.g., the piano roll described in 1.3). The notation in GesturAR can portray the inner articulation of different velocities inside a gesture: typically, a complex gesture does not have an even speed for its all duration but is characterised by an alternation of different velocities. This peculiar approach to musical time could be called *continuous rhythm*, as opposed to *discrete rhythm* (the one indicated by noteheads).

GesturAR also presents an embodied approach to the construction of the musical form. The disposition of gestures on the timeline, as a result of a bodily physical motion, poses an interesting perspective, although, at the current stage of development, the solutions offered are too limited (see next section).

4. LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE WORK

The technical quality for motion capture and rendering constitutes one of the limitations of the current version of GesturAR. The precision allowed by the use of LeapMotion is barely satisfying. The device has been designed to detect bare hands or hands while holding a pen or an object with similar shape. When the finger is pressing against the instrument (tam-tam, in this case), positional errors arise (trajectories tend to be subjected to random deviations from the original gesture). Another limit in the use of LeapMotion consists in the need to always keep the hands in the limited Field of View (FOV) of the sensor (150 x 135 degrees). This limitation might be solved through the use of motion capture gloves (not using magnetometers) or similar equipment. The quality of rendering is limited by the low resolution of the front facing cameras mounted on the Vive (420p). Further enhancements would include the use of a third-party front facing stereo VR camera (such as Stereolab's ZED Mini) or the adoption of a see-through device, such as Microsoft's HoloLens 2. However, in this

case, the limited FOV (43 x 29 degrees) might make the device unsuitable for this specific application. Other see-through devices have a similar or smaller FOV.

Although the representation of trajectories can precisely resemble speed and position over time of the original gesture, the interpreter cannot follow said trajectory as soon as it appears, due to the physiological reaction time. Instead, the performer would wait until a part of the trajectory has been shown before starting his/her own movement. Therefore, the notation would be followed with some degree of approximation. This fact is not necessarily a limit, as it is due to biological factors and should be perceived as a characteristic rather than a shortcoming.

Drawbacks can be found in the compositional dimension of GesturAR. The system so far allows the construction of very simple musical forms with no possibility of overlapping or superimposing gestures. The long-range temporal organization is left to an approximate perception of distance between blocks on the timeline, with no system for accurately structuring the occurrence of events. The current version of GesturAR does not allow the indication of dynamics, although the speed of the gesture itself might be considered, in some circumstances, as a dynamic mark. The notation can only work on instruments that have a surface to play on, like tam-tam, drums, piano strings. Such a form of notation could not be used for instruments such as woodwinds or brasses.

At the current stage, an evaluation experiment has yet to be realized. In order to assess the actual usefulness of the system, different parameters should be evaluated, with performers, composers and non-musicians as participants to the experiment(s). The main aspects to evaluate would be: time effectiveness of the system (both for composing and learning a piece), accuracy of the performance (comparing an AR system with a normally written score) and perceived usefulness.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This paper is about GesturAR, a system for the real-time notation of gesture and embodied composition in AR. The concept of embodied interactive notation has also been presented.

GesturAR allows the composer/performer to record trajectories in 4D space and time through the use of motion capture and AR equipment. Such gestures are intended to be performed on the surface of an instrument (for example, a tam-tam, as described in this research) as a collection of sampling points in space (3D cartesian coordinates and time values). By using a virtual UI, each saved trajectory is stored in memory and can be recalled, selected and played back (with a line moving from one sampling point to the next) on the instrument's surface. Trajectories can be adjusted on an AR timeline by using bare hands gestures. Once the timeline is processed, the time of occurrence of events is calculated proportionally (the red blocks' length is proportional to the duration of the gesture and the silence is calculated proportionally to the distance between blocks).

The concept of embodied interactive notation has been

proposed, defined as that form of notation that is created as a consequence of a gesture (detected through sensors) and that is a precise representation of that gesture in space and time, displayed as a trajectory or some other form of AR mark. Composer and performer experience the same performative dimension, although at different times and with different aims. In this context, the representation of rhythm shows a peculiar trait. In fact, this form of notation is not suitable for the indication of discrete time values (such as quaver or semiquaver) or different time proportions (still conceptually affine to the concept of subdivision of a longer duration value into shorter ones). Instead, it is the vehicle of a continuous representation of rhythm, where time proportions are represented over time and as different speeds inside a single gesture.

Limitations can be found in the robustness of the hand-tracking system making use of LeapMotion and in its compositional usability. Future developments of the research will include the use of motion capture gloves for reaching more reliable space sampling and capture data, the design of an evaluation experiment and improvements in the functionalities, such as the possibility of superimposition of different gestures.

Supporting material

Demonstration of the use of GesturAR at:
<https://www.gioannisantini.com/gesturar>

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